

THE MULTICODE CHARACTER OF A WORK OF ART

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ABSTRACT

The article concerns the phenomenon of multicode character of a text regarded as its semiotic heterogeneity. The author analyses interrelation between code heterogeneity, intertext and supertext.

Keywords: text; intertext; supertext; code; multicode character of a text.

The fundamental thesis put forward by Yu.M. Lotman: "Separate sign systems, although they are immanently organized structures, function only in unity, relying on each other" [6, p. 28]. Based on this thesis, as well as on the reflections of M.M. Bakhtin [3] on the structure of dialogically constructed texts and the teachings of V.V. Ivanov [5] about the relationship between the asymmetry of the brain and the asymmetry of semiotic systems, Russian scientists came to the conclusion about the multicode nature of culture. According to one of the fundamental theses of the Tartu-Moscow semiotic school, texts are divided into two varieties. Texts of the first variety are created within the framework of such communication, whose participants have very similar cognitive worlds. In such cases, the goal of communication is to broadcast information in accordance with the intent of the sender of the message, without distortion and without information loss. In this case, the text performs the function of a simple translator of the message, which is given a priori. These are elementary cases of information exchange in the process of communication.

Texts of the second type are created in those cases when new information appears in the communicative act. This happens when the sender and addressee have cognitive worlds that are very different. In such cases, the recipient of the message is not a simple "receiver" of information; he actively transforms it. In communication leading to the creation of texts of the first type, one code is used, which is the same for both communicants, while in communication leading to the creation of texts of the second

type, two codes are used (the sender's code and the recipient's code), and in these cases there is communication, according to essence of the matter, recoding information.

In these cases, changes in the content of the message are inevitable. Moreover, they are desirable. In the course of recoding, the text acquires a new, incremental content that was absent at the beginning of the act of communication. With the mass reading of the text, it has many interpretations ("the field of virtual interpretations" in the formulation of I.V. Arnold [1, p. 25]). Thus, the interpretation of I.V. Goethe, according to which the hypertrophy of intellectualism causes paralysis of the will; the interpretation of nineteenth-century German critics that the hero was a philosopher who professed the doctrine of inaction; interpretation of L.S. Vygotsky, according to which the hero has no power in his actions, since he is a puppet in the hands of Rock; the interpretation of Z. Freud, according to which the Prince of Denmark was unconsciously motivated by the Oedipus complex, etc.

It is hard to imagine that Shakespeare had all this in mind when he created tragedy. This whole complex of meanings grew out of the text of the play in subsequent centuries, in various cultural and historical contexts. In this sense, they say that the text of the second type (artistic, philosophical, religious-mythological, publicistic, etc.) is a generator of meaning, and therefore an intellectual system. Wed R. Barthes: "The text is understood as a space where the process of formation of meanings takes place" [2, p.424]. This is not about the work, but about the text. The word text comes from Lat. *textus* "weaving; the cloth". The interpretation of the text as a "sequence of verbal signs" [4, p.507] refers more to the work. Barthes, on the other hand, argued that the text has no beginning and end and that "it does not just have several meanings, it carries out the very plurality of meaning as such, which is caused by the spatial multilinearity of the signifiers from which it is woven" [2, p. 417]. The text is "completely woven from quotes, references, echoes; all these are languages of culture... that pass through the text and create a powerful stereophony" [2, p. 418].

The work is written in any one ethnic language and in this sense is monoglotic. The text is woven from many codes and in this sense is polyglot. The "threads" from which the text is woven include various codes, namely: other ethnic languages that underlie some citations and barbarisms; phraseological code, on the basis of which the idioms in the text are created; paremiological code (code of proverbs, sayings and other small folklore forms); sociolect codes; codes of territorial dialects; codes of aphorisms and citations, that is, inclusions from other texts that have a different semiotic specificity; allusion codes; codes of various normative and functional styles coexisting and intertwined in one text; character idiolect codes; a variety of non-verbal cultural codes that have acquired a verbal embodiment and become linguo-cultural codes;

codes of all kinds of themes and motifs characteristic of certain artistic movements and culture in general. All this is the interweaving of "threads" that form the "fabric" of the text.

The above interweaving is most clearly manifested in the dialogue, the participants of which differ markedly in cognitive, axiological, semiotic and other aspects. Let us give illustrative examples. In A.N. Tolstoy's fairy tale "The Golden Key" there is a hidden parallel with the theatrical life of Moscow at the beginning of the 20th century: the theater of Karabas - the theater of K.S. Stanislavsky, the theater of Papa Carlo - the theater of V.I. Nemirovich-Danchenko. In "Master and Margarita" M.A. Bulgakov, there is a modern realistic motif (Moscow of the 20th century), the motif of Sacred History (Jerusalem of the beginning of the 1st millennium AD, the Passion of Christ) and a mystical motif (Woland and his retinue).

In the stories and novellas of J. D. Salinger, Zen Buddhist motifs are found, etc. All this, according to Barth, is the cultural codes, the interweaving of which forms the text. Thus, the text functions against the background of other texts that form its context, and in interaction with them. This is where intertextuality comes in. "Every text is an inter-text with respect to some other text, but this intertextuality should not be understood in such a way that the text has some kind of origin; ... the text ... is formed from anonymous, elusive and at the same time already read quotes - from quotes without quotes" [2, p. 418].

In conclusion, let us comment on the relationship between the concepts "code" and "text".

Texts that are established and codified in a given culture acquire the status of precedent ones ([11]) and move "from the sphere of content to the conditional area of the code" [6, p. 46]. The syntagmatic formation (text), being cliched, turns into a paradigmatic formation - a code that models this or that name turns into a sign of this sphere. For example, a lot of precedent texts by Z. Freud formed the cognitive base of classical psychoanalysis, and its terminological system, containing Freud's theory, became the code for this branch of science. The name Oedipus complex has become a sign of the phenomenon of reality studied within the framework of this branch. Another example: M. Shelley's novel "Frankenstein" acquired the status of a precedent text, symbolizing the uncontrollability and pernicious consequences of scientific and technological progress; its plot scheme became a code, and its title became a sign-symbol of the corresponding phenomenon. This is how the accumulation and concentration of meaning is carried out, its paradigmaticization and condensation, leading to its entry into the language, which, as a result, is the thesaurus of accumulated cultural and historical experience and knowledge about the world.

The code of a precedent text, being used in other texts, serves as a model for a class of similar phenomena that are in homomorphic relations with it. It contributes to their understanding on the basis of the experience contained in it. For example, classical (antique, biblical, Shakespearean, etc.) motifs, explicitly or implicitly present in modern literary texts (“Ulysses” by J. Joyce, “The Labors of Hercules” by A. Christie, “Absalom, Absalom!” W. Faulkner, “Lady Macbeth of the Mtsensk District” by N.S. Leskova, “The Steppe King Lear” by I.S. Turgenev and others) act as models of the events described in these texts. This is one of the manifestations of the historical continuity of culture.

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